

THE PROBLEM OF FORMATION OF YOUNG POLYPHONIC MEANINGS IN MUSIC

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Abstract. In this article, the importance of polyphonic works and their connection with modern technologies, the role of young people in the formation of polyphonic works in music.

Keywords: problems, person, development, international music.

ПРОБЛЕМА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ МОЛОДЫХ ПОЛИФОНИЧЕСКИХ ЗНАЧЕНИЙ В МУЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье значение полифонических произведений и их связь с современными технологиями, роль молодежи в формировании полифонических произведений в музыке.

Ключевые слова: проблемы, человек, развитие, интернациональная музыка.

INTRODUCTION

The spiritual maturity of a person cannot be achieved without the art of music. After all, music has always played a special role in the life of our people. An example of this is the discovery of a bone flute three thousand three hundred years ago in the village of Muminabad near Samarkand. The sounds of music, expressing the most noble, noble, lofty and delicate human experiences, are performed by any people or nation. In particular, Abu Nasr Muhammad al-Farabi describes the art, especially poetry, as a reflection of the spiritual life of music and its deep impact on people. He also focuses on general scientific methodology, pedagogy, ethics, and aesthetics in his book The Great Music Book.

METODOLOGY AND MATERIALS

During the years of independence, continuing the traditions of our great ancestors, our country has been implementing programs and plans for the development of music. In particular, in order to preserve and study our classical musical heritage, to pass it on to the younger generation, many competitions and prestigious international music conferences are held regularly. [1] Today, significant results are being achieved in the cultural heritage of the Uzbek people, linguistics and literature, and other practical areas. In particular, it plays an important role in enhancing the effectiveness of national spiritual reforms in our country, the establishment of democratic principles, as well as the management of socio-political processes. "Most importantly, today, the art of music has a greater and stronger impact on the development of our young generation in the spirit of high spirituality than any other art form.

State Education Standards have been developed to further improve higher education music education. According to him, the goal of music science is to provide students with knowledge in various fields. It is also aimed at improving the professional level, technical development of the sound apparatus, development of artistic skills and education at a high artistic level. As a result of mastering this subject, the student is expected to have the knowledge, skills and abilities specified in the State Educational Standards, in particular: traditional music, masterpieces of composition and academic works; performance skills and analysis of works, thinking; the possibility and scope of different voices;

the nature of modern jazz and pop;
acoustic structure of sound;
activities in concerts and competitions;
have the skills and competencies to perform the execution practice.

RESULT

In the current process of globalization, not only advanced technologies, but also the art of music are entering our country with their high human qualities, refinements that reflect the beauty of nature. For example, Polyphony (a Latin word meaning "plural"). Polyphony is a form of pluralism based on artistic equality. There are usually three types of polyphony in the musical heritage of different peoples and in the work of composers:

- Auxiliary voice polyphony based on equal sounding of melody and accompanying variants;
- Simulated polyphony based on a single melody that goes from voice to voice;
- Contrast polyphony based on the simultaneous sound of several independent melodies;

Polyphony has been known in European polyphonic music since the ninth century, and its historical development is recognized in the works of representatives of the Dutch school, Palestrina and others, including I.S. Bach, G.F. Handel. In the twentieth century, the style was enriched in the works of I. Stravinsky, D. Shostakovich, P. Hindemith, B. Britten, V. Lyutoslavsky and others. Uzbek composers G. Mushel and T. Kurbanov in their works have paid special attention to polyphony and managed to connect it with the narrative and developmental features of the Uzbek musical heritage. Polyphony is included in the special music education system as a subject. In the middle of the 20th century, Uzbek musicologists also used a new method, polymondia, based on a combination of polyphony and monody.

This style is determined by the timbre of certain words, the direction of different sounds, the specificity of the sounds of instruments or ensembles. Initially, the polyphony was formed in the instrumental melodies and some songs of composers such as K. Jabborov, M. Mirzayev and, in particular, F. Sodikov. Later it was reflected in the works of N. Kulabdullayev "Don't think", A. Ismailov "Meeting", "Don't ask Holim", "Fountain", "Wedding". We can see this style in our national classical music.

IN CONCLUSION

In short, in educating young people, we need to pay more attention to the harmonization of European world music and our national music. Because beautiful music teaches a person to feel delicate beauty. There is nothing wrong with a person who feels good. Beautiful music is a means of educating the perfect person. This means that it is important to create conditions for young people to enjoy new ideas, innovative technologies, masterpieces of national and world music culture, as well as examples of modern pop art in the formation and protection of various trends. Since every sound or voice in polyphony has an equal commonality, it reflects the social and spiritual unity of the peoples and nations of the world.

Polyphony - the idea of creativity sounds like a bell of peace in the new world. Polyphony calls for the unification of the peoples of the world. Polyphony encourages problem-solving together. Because music is only a source of goodness.

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